

Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 39 to 43

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The work is also available at author's site:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19723>

Abstract

*This work bring different ways of representing prime magic squares. These are of types: **blocks, block-bordered, concentric, nested**, etc. This work is for the orders 39 to 43. For prime magic squares of orders 6 to 38 author's work [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. In case of prime magic squares of orders 41 and 43, the compositions of order 39 are applied over 41 and 43 considering **single and double-layer borders** representing as **block-bordered prime magic squares**, with internal blocks based on different compositions of of prime magic squares of order 39.*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260
	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9 pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc										369
31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11		369
30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16		369
35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15		369
22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56		369
21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61		369
26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60		369
67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47		369
66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52		369
71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51		369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums.

1.3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10	mgc											505
	91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505	
	13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88	505	
	89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505	
	11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505	
	96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505	
	1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505	
	93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505	
	7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505	
	95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505	
	9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

The blocks of order 8 are **equal sums** pandiagonal magic squares of order 10.

1.4 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

1.5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• Blocks of Order 3

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
870	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• **Blocks of Order 4**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870	
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870	
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870	
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870	
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870	
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870	
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870	
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870	
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870	
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870	
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870	
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

• **Blocks of Order 6**

12	mgc													870
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870	
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870	
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870	
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870	
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870	
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870	
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870	
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870	
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870	
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870	
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870	
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author's work [29, 30, 31]. The aim of this work write magic squares with blocks of order 4 with distinct prime number entries.

Based on the idea of blocks, block-borders, etc. given above, we shall concentrate our work in this direction on **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts.

2 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Orders 39 to 43

This work brings different ways representing magic squares in prime numbers. Initial aim is represent in terms of blocks. Some of possibilities led us to concentric or single-layer bordered magic squares. It includes blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, etc. Sometimes these blocks are of **equal** or **different** magic sums. This work is for the orders 39 to 43. For the previous orders refer authors work [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. Also there are two more works on prime magic squares recently done by the author. The first one is on **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic squares** of orders 120 and 121 [8]. The second one is **block-structured** prime magic squares of order 1220 multiples of 4 [9].

Whenever, we write **prime magic square**, it means that the magic squares are composed of **distinct prime number entries**, except in few cases, where the central constant 1000003 is repeating. It is considered only in case of odd order primes magic squares, where we need the **equal sums** magic squares.

This work is for the **prime magic squares** of orders 39 to 43. The table below give different representations for each order:

Order	Representations
39	07 (01-07)
40	11 (08-18)
41	07 (19-25)
42	15 (26-40)
43	07 (41-47)
Total	47

2.1 Prime Magic Squares of Order 39

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 39 with different representations. We know that $39 := 3 \times 13$. It means that most of the blocks are composition of prime magic squares of orders 3 and 13.

Example 1. Different Sums Blocks of Order 3. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 39

1223749	638857	1194979	97003	1845427	186679	1966807	462727	1815103	568699	194119	629737	1821613	1866283	488263	1877857	1618909	209647	1081813	211789	1910107	379993	1141573	693619	874723	1004119	474289	1676869	1054219	790519	1882963	635197	1543999	520279	417577	1944373	26227	1259983	233419	1536013
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It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 40. It is composed of **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 5. The internal blocks of orders 3 are also **different sums** prime magic squares. Moreover, in each center we have a fixed prime constant, i.e., 1000003.

Example 12. Different Sums Concentric Blocks of Order 8. Let's consider following prime magic square of order 40

2.3 Prime Magic Squares of Order 41

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 41. Since 41 is a prime number, we don't have factors of 41. In this we shall use the factor of order 39 and then create a **single-layer border** resulting in prime magic square of order 41, These type of magic squares we call as **block-bordered prime magic squares**. Let's see some examples below

Example 19. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. *Let's consider following prime magic square of order 41*

99907	99949	99406	100608	100099	100603	99297	100107	100273	99623	100102	100108	99789	100133	100428	99436	100138	100146	99713	100158	101079	98823	100162	100467	99370	100180	101017	98803	100177	100822	99803	100198	101221	98507	100273	100729	99067	100234	100369	99429	100045		
100243	56497	164509	79003	86077	190017	23905	97792	68020	134188	138336	7210	154453	73237	137677	89159	73066	144499	82443	117843	148339	167297	152839	68403	78753	70549	186063	43396	180807	21139	98059	126196	13609	160195	97888	151449	50662	14394	18854	97060	99753		
101293	122509	100003	77497	37827	100003	16217	136396	100003	63604	11616	100003	83887	11591	100003	84081	10937	100003	9062	14941	100003	5058	2591	100003	1740	7285	100003	1271	1725	100003	1827	1339	100003	6601	5277	100003	1472	1826	100003	1733	9870		
9851	12100	3549	1435	1760	9982	1192	6581	1319	1022	4554	1927	6166	1108	6239	1267	1175	5550	1269	3270	1851	8212	1212	1315	969	4716	1566	1393	1294	1019	1788	1919	3980	1863	7380	1493	4855	1021	1029	1145	1856	1014	
10025	7600	1594	6451	1108	1914	1699	4064	1279	1314	7681	9821	1249	6759	1555	7683	1055	7171	1872	6993	1520	7801	6221	1659	718	1534	2191	1246	9313	1605	4634	2672	1868	8646	1142	1894	1668	6545	1950	3948	9974		
1019	8850	1000	1149	1590	1000	409	1907	1000	921	1481	1000	5185	1092	1000	907	1816	1000	1834	1080	1000	919	1096	1000	903	711	1000	1288	5320	1000	146	159	1000	402	1526	1000	47	74	1000	12	980		
9776	1354	405	123	300	180	891	685	720	159	750	101	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	123

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 41, where the internal block of prime magic square of order 39 is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 3. It has repeated fixed number entries.

Example 21. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 41

1500823	369079	4357	283957	1633573	108793	968137	1816063	1723333	68473	968329	363277	517087	336703	1447123	1264009	1959487	726697	154579	1571029	758179	229693	1669399	1914769	1944373	1791277	473419	1386037	609517	1445827	1612609	1212259	1408843	1161547	989533	583267	944893	612679	1488499	489817	488779
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It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 41, where the internal block of prime magic square of order 39 is composed of **different sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 13.

Example 24. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let’s consider following **prime magic square** of order 41

A large 41x41 grid of numbers representing a prime magic square, with each cell containing a unique integer value. The grid is organized into concentric blocks, with a central 39x39 block nested within the outer 41x41 frame.

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 41, where the internal block of prime magic square of order 39 is composed of **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 13.

Example 25. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 41

1743523	1999219	192097	536773	1878139	874477	699529	1105813	222493	1297477	1188619	806857	1082083	372943	425977	461803	1999969	1736179	1895833	88969	731719	1555999	499669	433663	1590937	254869	578533	1745923	640279	466723	1959967	1677037	1876009	807127	1888753	150919	641863	277177	128923	1882963	1358689	243613
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It is block-structured prime magic square of order 42 composed of equal sums concentric prime magic squares of order 14.

Example 34. Different Sums Blocks of Order 14. Let's consider following prime magic square of order 42

2074801	2090089	666067	1060567	1275067	1724761	1795987	1304389	741787	1377829	807637	394879	2031187	485899	538927	471007	1081291	895003	292471	1059067	1009873	351397	876181	416677	221083	309811	1035187	799723	290593	968467	493447	1551619	321247	484867	1759987	1505083	1793497	1349119	1217407	611497	582643	1882009
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*It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 42 composed of **different sums** prime magic squares of order 14. Blocks of order 14 are nested with blocks of order 12. The blocks of order 12 are again composed of **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3.*

Example 35. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 14. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 42

629383	627379	1248979	396997	1578289	1206553	1805593	1929289	645703	1232689	1067359	688783	880057	62989	1571833	1731937	792049	1514179	213649	678739	1701493	1219549	537379	198769	118219	1868983	1816567	36697	1282417	1439527	360853	1251667	1844707	597049	672703	1511047	378289	1663477	1387189	347167	603937	660013
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*It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 42 composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 14. Blocks of order 14 are nested with blocks of order 12. The blocks of order 12 are again composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 4.*

Example 38. Different Sums Blocks of Order 14. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 42

2.5 Prime Magic Squares of Order 43

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 43. Since 43 is a prime number, we don't have factors of 43. In this we shall use the factor of order 39 and then create two single-layer borders resulting in prime magic square of order 43, These type of magic squares we call as block-bordered prime magic square. Let's see some examples below

Example 41. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. *Let's consider following prime magic square of order 43*

3 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

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